

UDC 021.85(477.63) «18/20»

LUCHKA L. M.

Scientific Library, Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine), e-mail:

Luchka64@i.ua, ORCID: 0000-0002-1792-2349

LIBRARY BOOK EXCHANGE: HISTORY AND CURRENT STATE

Objective. The purpose of the article is to highlight book exchange as an important source of book acquisition process in the libraries of Katerinoslav - Dnipropetrovsk. The object is libraries of different subordination as a system of collection-forming documents. **Methods.** Analytical-synthetic, system-structural, comparative and statistical methods are used during the research in accordance with the task. **Results.** The author revealed the peculiarities of book exchange process in the libraries of educational institutions, scientific societies of Katerynoslavshchyna. The exchange of publications with Kyiv, Galician and Lviv institutions is proved to be useful and important. The author retraced process of cooperation of city public libraries on local literature acquisition. Libraries and reading rooms of higher, secondary and lower agricultural educational institutions received professional publications of Katerinoslav societies free of charge. The article gives a picture of the current state of document exchange in the libraries of Dnipropetrovsk region. The constant source of library acquisition is territorial and domestic professional book exchange. **Conclusions.** Book exchange is an important component of the process of acquisition of high quality stock in Ukrainian libraries. This process was actively carried out by Katerinoslav libraries in the 19th - early 20th centuries. Throughout history the book exchange has proven to be a necessary and useful source of acquisition and high quality service in the implementation of complex reader requests. Document exchange in the 21st century in Dnipropetrovsk region is changing its format (transition to e-resources), but remains an important source in the process of creating high quality collections.

Keywords: book exchange; libraries of educational institution; societies; Katerinoslav Governorate; Dnipropetrovsk region

Introduction

Library science studies the history of libraries of different subordination in the main areas of activity: acquisition, services, information and reference work, etc. Book exchange is an important component of the process of stock acquisition, the ultimate goal of which is to meet the needs of readers. Book exchange helps to create and store complete collections of books and periodicals (valuable in content and design) for users. The research topic is due to the problematic aspects of the development of modern libraries in Ukraine, which continue the tradition, update their service using e-documents.

Methods

Analytical-synthetic, system-structural, comparative and statistical methods of scientific research are developed and used in accordance with the tasks.

Results and Discussion

In the second half of the 19th century the process of distribution of book products became more active, so the role of book exchange in processes of cooperation between libraries was growing. From 1877 to 1916, the Commission on International Exchange of Scientific and Fictional Editions operated under the Ministry of Education. Domestic book exchange during the tsar period was limited. Book exchange means free transfer of printed works from one library to another for permanent use and is an effective source of collection development by means of documents that were not distributed through the book trade network. The Ukrainian Library

Encyclopedia (ULE) provides a definition of the modern term of “book exchange” as interlibrary document exchange between libraries within the country. Its purpose is to complete the existing library collections, improve their quality and free them from unnecessary duplicate and non-core documents (National Library of Ukraine named after Yaroslav the Wise, 2021).

The role and significance of book exchange is clearly defined by the Ukrainian librarian K. I. Rubinsky: since each library is a reflection of its epoch, the study of collections allows to imagine comprehensively the realities of life at that time (Vaneev, p. 151). According to another scientist, a well-known bibliographer N. A. Rubakin, the library core (book collection) is the center of gravity of each library, due to the content of which the library must operate and meet the appropriate level of education (Rubakin, pp. 126-159).

At the end of the 19th century Katerinoslav city public library with the support of the Chairman of the Library Council G. A. Zalyubovsky had business relations with 10 libraries and received free books from six scientific societies. In 1910, Katerinoslav Library sent to the colleagues of Mariupol City Library at their request 7 titles, 396 volumes of duplicate magazines, in the public reading room of Yenakiievo station – 6 titles, 432 volumes (*Otchet Yekaterinoslavskoy Gorodskoy Obshchestvennoy Biblioteki*, 1894, pp. 14, 30).

In the early 20th century exchange of experience was an important area of professional development of library staff. Under these conditions the reports of Nikolaev, Kharkiv, Odessa, Sevastopol, Yalta societies of library science arrived to Katerinoslav city library and they contained interesting information. In addition, in 1911 the library of the Russian Academy of Sciences received duplicate copies of "Vestnik Yuga" newspaper from the city public library (*Otchet Yekaterinoslavskoy Gorodskoy Obshchestvennoy Biblioteki*, 1912, p. 5).

In the 19th century book exchange was important and necessary for Katerinoslav educational institutions. Teachers of Katerinoslav classical gymnasium sent their works to other educational institutions only after the obligatory consideration by the trustee of Odessa educational district. With the support of the gymnasium director Ya. D. Grakhov, the institution closely cooperated with the Russian Geographical Society through the exchange of local publications (1849). The classical gymnasium exchanged books with well-known educational institutions of St. Petersburg, the oldest institutions of the empire: Richelieu Lyceum and Vilnius University (1831). I. S. Afanasyev, a teacher of mathematical sciences, the inspector of the gymnasium, was the head of the library since 1819. Since 1841 he was responsible for the work of the bookshop and actively cooperated with Kharkiv University. A. I. Bartashevych, a Senior Lecturer in Latin Language at the gymnasium, made a certain contribution in this direction. His activity as a bookshop head in 1831–1841 was useful for the development of the fundamental library (Lokot, 1908, pp. 98, 134).

At the end of the 19th century with the support of the governorate zemstvo, the library of Katerinoslav First Real School received from Gnedinsky Crafts School various textbooks to a total value of about 3,000 rubles. The publications became a powerful base for the student audience during the educational process (*Otchet o Sostoyanii Yekaterinoslavskogo Realnogo Uchilishcha*, 1894, p. 25).

The activity of the library of Katerinoslav Higher Mining School was important in this direction. Since the beginning of its existence, the management of the educational institution paid special attention to the formation of high-quality and modern collections of subordinate libraries. In 1906, under the leadership of S. M. Suchkov, the Higher Mining School published more than 50 titles of textbooks and manuals, which were distributed among local libraries and other institutions. According to reports, it is known that through book exchange the school received books from official bodies and institutions: the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Railways and the Mining Department (Rubin, 1909, p. 74).

A system of cooperation was established with more than 20 higher educational institutions, including St. Volodymyr's University in Kyiv, Kyiv Polytechnic Institute, Kharkiv University, Novorossiysk University, Kazan University, Tomsk University, Warsaw Polytechnic Institute, etc. (1904). Due to book exchange, the institution library collection annually grew by 500 copies having the latest multidisciplinary literature, among which about 100 copies were educational literature. In 1908, the library transferred the editions of Katerinoslav Higher Mining School to other organizations and institutions by book exchange, having received 90 titles of Russian and Ukrainian periodicals in return. Book exchange of duplicate editions was carried out based on correspondence with the employees responsible for this work of other libraries or scientific societies. (*Otchet o Sostoyanii i Deystviyakh Yekaterinoslavskogo Gornogo Uchilishcha*, 1912, pp. 45-47).

In the early 20th century thanks to book exchange, Katerinoslav Prosvita Society received Ukrainian books and periodicals from E. P. Cherepovsky's Ukrainian bookshop in Kyiv. Friendly and professional relations connected "Prosvita" and Katerynodar. The libraries of the latter received Katerinoslav magazine "Dnipro Waves" ("Dniprovi Khvyli"). Significant work was carried out by the society for the distribution of its own publications on the history of the native land to Ukrainian bookshops. "Prosvita" Library Commission exchanged Ukrainian publications with Galician and Russian relevant societies and institutions. In 1917, members of "Prosvita" society in the village of Pereshchepine in Novomoskovsk district asked publishers and Ukrainian authors to send their publications and works to the library. The educational institution had its own publishing collection, copies of which were sent by members of the society to Kyiv "Prosvita". It was useful to cooperate with "Literary and Scientific Bulletin" bookshop and "Ukrainian bookshop" (*Dniprovi Khvyli*, 1913).

Opened in 1874, the Free Women's School of the Society of Guardianship of Women's Education in Katerynoslav received 9 titles of books (1878/79) from the editors of "Education and Training" magazine. Thanks to the request of the cultural and educational leader, teacher O. O. Andrievskiy, the school library received as a donation from the editors the following magazines: "Family and School", "Picturesque Review", "Nature and People", "Education and Training". Communication with the Committee for the Distribution of Useful Books was fruitful. As a result, the school library received 255 copies of books, brochures, serial editions in the early 80's of the 19th century.

The book exchange between Katerinoslav Scientific Archival Commission (1903) and Katerinoslav Scientific Society (1901) was useful. The collection of scientific literature and periodicals was formed through exchange with scientific institutions and societies. The local edition "Chronicles of Katerinoslav Scientific Archival Commission" systematically published a list of new books received by the society. Through active communication with Lviv University, the library collection of the Commission was enriched with thorough works on the history of southern and western Russia by the Ukrainian leader, Professor M. S. Hrushevsky. In 1910, members of Katerinoslav Academic Archival Commission petitioned Orenburg and Poltava Academic Archival Commissions for exchanging books. Initiative librarians V. F. Adamov, J. V. Lokot, V. V. Danilov were responsible for this activity. Katerynoslav activists facilitated the establishment of book exchange relations of the Commission, officially addressing certain scientific institutions and using personal contacts. According to the report of the Chairman of the Society A. S. Synyavsky, book exchange took place with organizations and publishing houses of Chernihiv, Kharkiv, Kyiv, and Odessa. V. O. Bidnov contributed to the restoration of library relations with colleagues. He supported acquisitions of the latest pedagogical works by historian S. V. Farfarovsky (*Letopis Yekaterinoslavskoy Uchenoy Arkhivnoy Komissii*, 1909; Kunanets, 2011).

In 1910, at one of the meetings, a report was prepared on the receipt of 13 publications valuable in content from Odessa, Kharkiv, Volyn, Chernihiv and Poltava. Correspondence was conducted with 10 archival commissions, Shevchenko Scientific Society in Lviv, and Kyiv Scientific Society. In 1911 the "History of Kharkiv University" by the Ukrainian historian and public leader D. I. Bagaliy was added to the collections of the scientific library, while the "Chronicles of Katerinoslav Scientific Archival Commission" were sent to the colleagues (*Letopis Yekaterinoslavskoy Uchenoy Arkhivnoy Komissii*, 1911, p. 270).

In Katerinoslav region of the early 20th century the Scientific and Technical Society, established in 1910 with the support of the chemist L. V. Pisarzhevsky played an important role in dissemination of technical knowledge and quality training of technical staff. The society took care of the library, which had technical literature and was available to residents. In 1913 the technical library received from colleagues 6 titles of professional journals, publications of Kiev Polytechnic Institute and Crimean technical institutions. Librarian L. L. Ivanov was responsible for the acquisition of modern periodicals.

In the late 19th - early 20th century the activity of professional societies intensified in Katerynoslav. They include the Beekeepers (1898), Gardening (1893), Hunting (1910–1917), and Agriculture (1915–1917) societies. All societies were united by the presence of a professional printed body. The Beekeepers society published their magazine "Bee", the Society of Gardening had "Vesnik", the Society of Agriculture published "Southern Economy" magazine. Publications of Katerinoslav societies were sent to zemstvo libraries of Katerinoslav Governorate and to scientific institutions of other governorates. By means of free exchange, the Society of Beekeepers sent 104 copies of its publications, having received in return 90 copies of new publications (*Otchet o Deyatelnosti Yekaterinoslavskogo Obshchestva Pchelovodov*, 1913, p. 4). One copy of "Southern Economy" magazine was sent to England (1915-1916), which indicates a high information level of the local publication. Instead, the library of the agricultural society kept reports and works of special societies in its collections. According to the decision of the society council, libraries and reading rooms of higher, secondary and lower agricultural educational establishments received the professional publications free of charge and in turn enriched the collections of Katerinoslav institution with their own periodicals (115 titles) (1915) (*Otchet o Deyatelnosti Yekaterinoslavskogo Gubernskogo Obshchestva Selskogo Khozyaystva*, 1916, pp. 21, 89-97).

Historical roots of book exchanging have a traditional continuation in the development of modern libraries in Dnipropetrovsk region. Document exchange operates in the identified main areas.

- ✓ Exchange collections are created and operate in the following libraries: Dnipropetrovsk Regional Universal Scientific Library, Scientific Library of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (DNU).
- ✓ Domestic (official) book exchange is carried out in Oles Honchar DNU Scientific Library, Scientific and Technical Library of Dnipro National University of Railway Transport, Dniprovsk State Technical University Library, Dnipropetrovsk Regional Universal Scientific Library. Most libraries solve these problems on their own.
- ✓ The most reliable and widespread is the territorial book exchange, thanks to which a large number of libraries in the region receive individual copies and complete collections. Permanent partners are Dnipropetrovsk Regional Universal Scientific Library, Dnipro National University, Dnipropetrovsk National Historical Museum, Ukraine's first ATO Museum, South-Eastern Department of the Ukrainian Institute of National Remembrance, Ukrainian Institute for Holocaust Studies.

- ✓ A constant source of stock acquisition are donations from colleagues and publishers (specialized, medical, technical, agricultural literature etc.)
- ✓ DNU Scientific Library, Scientific and Technical Library of “Dnipro Polytechnic”, Ukrainian State University of Chemical Technology and Dnipropetrovsk Regional Universal Scientific Library have foreign partners. Cooperation continues with European countries (Poland, Germany), the United States and Canada.

Libraries of higher education institutions of Dnipropetrovsk region closely cooperate with colleagues from Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Lviv Polytechnic National University, V. N Karazin Kharkiv National University, Odesa Mechnikov National University, V. I. Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine, Kharkiv State Scientific Library named after V. G. Korolenko and regional state libraries.

Conclusions

Book exchange is an important component of the process of acquisition of quality collections in Ukrainian libraries. It was actively carried out by Katerinoslav libraries in the 19th - early 20th centuries. Throughout history the book exchange has proven to be a necessary and useful source of acquisition and high quality service in the implementation of complex reader requests. Having a long-standing historical basis, document exchange in the 21st century in Dnipropetrovsk region is changing its format (transition to e-resources). Despite the smaller volume and some financial problems, the book exchange remains a constant source in the process of creating multidisciplinary collections.

REFERENCES

Dniprovi khvyli. (1913). 5. 79-80. (in Ukrainian)

Kunanets, N. (2011). Formuvannia fondiv naukovykh knyhozbiren Lvova shliakhom knyhoobminu v kintsi KhIKh – na pochatku KhKh st. *Bibliotchna Planeta*, 2, 17-19. (in Ukrainian)

Letopis Yekaterinoslavskoy uchenoy arkhivnoy komissii (YeUAK). (1909). 5, 12-14. (in Russian)

Lokot, Ya. V. (1908). *Istoricheskie zapiski o stoletnemu sushchestvovanii Yekaterinoslavskoy klassicheskoy gimnazii, 1805-1905.* Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

National Library of Ukraine named after Yaroslav the Wise. (2021). *Ukrainska bibliotchna entsyklopediia.* Retrieved from <https://ube.nlu.org.ua> (in Ukrainian)

Otchet Yekaterinoslavskoy gorodskoy obshchestvennoy biblioteki za 1893 g. (1894). Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Otchet Yekaterinoslavskoy gorodskoy obshchestvennoy biblioteki za 1911 g. (1912). Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Otchet o deyatelnosti Yekaterinoslavskogo gubernskogo obshchestva selskogo khozyaystva, 1 yanvary 1915 – 1 yanvary 1916 gg. (1916). Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Otchet o deyatelnosti Yekaterinoslavskogo obshchestva pchelovodov za 1912 g. (1913). Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Otchet o deyatelnosti Yekaterinoslavskoy uchenoy arkhivnoy komissii, 1909-1910 gg. (1911). *Letopis Yekaterinoslavskoy uchenoy arkhivnoy komissii*, 7, 266-271.

Otchet o sostoyanii Yekaterinoslavskogo realnogo uchilishcha za 1893-1894 uch. god. (1894). Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Otchet o sostoyanii i deystviyakh Yekaterinoslavskogo gornogo uchilishcha za 1911 g. (1912). Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Rubakin, N. A. (1893). Knyzhnoe oskudenye. *Russkoe Bohatstvo*, 1(2), 126-159. (in Russian)

Rubin, P. G. (1909). *Istoricheskiy ocherk vozniknoveniya Yekaterinoslavskogo vysshego gornogo uchilishcha i ego deyatelnosti za 1899 – 1909 gg.* Yekaterinoslav. (in Russian)

Vaneev, A. N. (2003). *Razvitie bibliotekovedcheskoy mysli v Rossii (XI - nachalo XX vv.)*. Moscow, Russia. (in Russian)

LUCHKA L. M.

Наукова бібліотека, Дніпровський національний університет імені Олеся Гончара (Дніпро, Україна), e-mail: Luchka64@i.ua, ORCID: 0000-0002-1792-2349

БІБЛІОТЕЧНИЙ КНИГООБМІН: ІСТОРІЯ ТА СУЧАСНИЙ СТАН

Мета полягає у висвітленні книгообміну як важливого джерела процесу комплектування фондів у бібліотеках Катеринославщини – Дніпропетровщини. Об'єктом виступають бібліотеки різного підпорядкування як системи фондоутворюючих документів. **Методика.** Під час дослідження використовувались аналітико-синтетичний, системно-структурний, порівняльний та статистичний методи, які застосовувались відповідно до завдання. **Результати.** Виявлено особливості книгообмінного процесу в бібліотеках навчальних закладів, наукових товариств Катеринославщини. Доведено, що корисним і важливим був обмін виданнями з київськими, галицькими та львівськими установами. Прослідковано процес співпраці міських громадських бібліотек щодо поповнення фондів краєзнавчою літературою. Фахові видання катеринославських товариств отримували безкоштовно бібліотеки і читальні вищих, середніх та нижчих сільськогосподарських навчальних закладів. Створена картина сучасного стану документообміну у бібліотеках Дніпропетровщини. Постійним джерелом поповнення фондів є територіальний та внутрішньодержавний фаховий книгообмін. **Висновки.** Книгообмін як вагома складова процесу комплектування якісних фондів українських бібліотек активно здійснювався катеринославськими бібліотеками у ХІХ – початку ХХ ст. Протягом історії книгообмін довів, що є необхідним і корисним джерелом поповнення фондів та якісного обслуговування під час виконання складних читацьких запитів. Документообмін у ХХІ ст. на Дніпропетровщині змінює формат (перехід на е-ресурси), проте залишається важливим джерелом у процесах створення якісних фондів.

Ключові слова: книгообмін; бібліотеки навчальних закладів; товариства; Катеринославська губернія; Дніпропетровська область

Received: 12.07.2021

Accepted: 08.12.2021